

Why isn't a free Electron repelled into Sky according to the Earth E-field?

The Electromagnetic Theory of Gravitation.

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Abstract

As everyone knows Braun's cathode ray tubes (e.g. "old TVs") work and free electrons at low velocity are not rejected into sky. This simple observation is not self-evident at all because the electron is an absolutely highly negatively charged ($q = 1e$) particle and possesses only a small amount of mass ($m = m_e$). In terms of these data and regarding to the earth's E-field one would expect that the electron is rejected from earth fast and strongly. It will be shown here that taking the new physical quantity z into account and extending the mass charge unification to the gravitational and electric field will lead to an easy explanation of this well known physical phenomenon. Thereby a electromagnetic theory of gravitation is presented.

Résumé

Comme chacun le sait cathodiques des tubes de Brown (par exemple "vieille télé") travail et des électrons libres à faible vitesse ne sont pas rejetées dans le ciel. Ce simple constat n'est pas évident du tout parce que l'électron est absolument très chargé négativement ($q = 1e$) et poss de particules esses seulement une petite quantité de masse ($m = m_e$). En termes de données et de synthèse concernant à la une E-champ terrestre s'attendrait ne l'électron est rejeté de la terre et presque fortement. Il sera présenté ici ne prenant la nouvelle quantité z physique en compte et extension de l'unification de la masse de lots pour le champ gravitationnel et électrique entraînera une explication facile de ce phénomène physique bien connu. Ainsi une théorie électromagnétique de la gravitation est présentée.

Keywords: Gravitation, Electromagnetism, Maxwell Equations, General Relativity

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Introduction

Calculation of the Electron Acceleration According to the Earth E-Field

As written in physics textbooks by different authors (1),(2),(3),(4),(5) the earth is surrounded by a strong E-field ranging from 100 N/C (Landa et al 1995) to 150 N/C (most other authors as Zitzewitz et al. and others). However according to this E-field an electron on earth should be accelerated according to the following laws into the sky:

$$\text{Force on the electron: } F = E \cdot q = E \cdot e = 150 \frac{N}{C} \cdot 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-17} N$$

$$\text{Leading to an acceleration of: } a = \frac{E \cdot e}{m_e} = \frac{150 \cdot 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19}}{9.1 \cdot 10^{-31}} \cdot \frac{m}{s^2}$$

$$a = \frac{2.4 \cdot 10^{-17}}{9.1 \cdot 10^{-31}} \cdot \frac{m}{s^2}$$

$$a = 2.6 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot \frac{m}{s^2}$$

To give a comparison the acceleration due to gravity is given by only $g=9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$. Therefore the E-field driven acceleration of an electron should be 10^{12} higher than the acceleration due to gravity. So why isn't the electron rejected into sky? An explanation of this phenomenon can be given by transferring the unification of electricity and gravity as it already has been done by forming the quantity z towards the electrostatic and gravitational field laws as will be done in the following.

Transferring the Quantity z to the Fields and Connecting the Maxwells equations of electrostatics to the Maxwell-Einsteins equations of General Relativity (GR)

The new quantity z fits very well into the existing structure of physics. Substitution of q through z, and of the charge-density through the z-density in Maxwell's equations will lead to a united equation consisting of both equations at the same time: Maxwell's equations of electrostatics as well as of Maxwell-Einstein's equations of Einstein's general theory of relativity (GR). So both equations can be derived easily at the same time. In this way, the considerable morphological homology of the equations can easily be explained as will be seen in the subsequent formulas. Explanation of the field terms used: E, B: Maxwell fields; g, C: corresponding Maxwell Einstein fields of GR; Phi, D: new defined summarized fields which are defined by $\Phi = E+g$ and $D = B+C$, and which also can be defined more correctly by $\Phi = E+g i$ and $D = B+C i$ (i: imaginary unit).

$$\nabla E = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon}; \nabla B = 0; \nabla \times E = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial t}; \nabla \times B = \mu_0 \rho v + \frac{\partial E}{c^2 \partial t} \quad (\text{Maxwell Equations}) \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla g = -\frac{\rho_m}{\epsilon_g}; \nabla C = 0; \nabla \times g = -\frac{\partial C}{\partial t}; \nabla \times C = \mu_g \rho_m v + \frac{\partial g}{c^2 \partial t} \quad (\text{Maxwell Einstein Equations})(2)$$

Def: new fields Φ and D

$$\Phi \equiv E + gi; \quad D \equiv B + Ci \quad (3)$$

If Φ is acting on an electron e using $z=bq+mi=(bq,m)$, with $b=11 \cdot 10^9$ kg/C this can be written as follows. For more details regarding the (bq,m) - formalism see Arneeth (6).

$$\Rightarrow F = \Phi_z = (E + ig)(bq + mi) = Ebq - gm + Emi + igbq, \text{ leading to } F = ma \approx (E - g)bq \quad (4)$$

The relation (4) can easily be tested by determining the homogeneity or in-homogeneity of ions accelerated in the earth E- and g- field.

$$\nabla \Phi = \nabla(E + gi) = \nabla E + \nabla gi = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} - \frac{\rho_m}{\epsilon_g} = \frac{bqe}{\epsilon_0 bV} + \frac{mi}{\epsilon_g V/i} = \frac{z}{V\epsilon} = \frac{\rho_z}{\epsilon} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon_g \epsilon_0 b}{\epsilon_g + \epsilon_0 bi}; \quad \frac{b}{\epsilon} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0}; \quad \epsilon_0 b = \epsilon; \quad \epsilon_g = \epsilon \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla \Phi = \nabla(E + gi) = \frac{z}{V\epsilon} = \frac{\rho_z}{\epsilon}; \quad \nabla D = \nabla B + \nabla C = 0; \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \times \Phi = \nabla \times (E + gi) = \nabla \times E + \nabla \times gi = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial D}{\partial t} = -\dot{D} \quad (8)$$

$$\nabla \times \Phi = -\dot{D} \quad (9)$$

$$\nabla \times D = \nabla \times (B + C) = \nabla \times B + \nabla \times C = \mu_0 \rho v + \frac{\partial E}{c^2 \partial t} + \mu_g \rho_m v + \frac{\partial g}{c^2 \partial t} = \mu_0 \rho_z v + \frac{1}{c^2} \dot{\Phi} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\mu_0}{b} = \mu_g; \mu_g \cdot b = \mu_0 \quad (11)$$

According to relation (4) the force acting on a free electron can be written as

$F = ma \approx (E - g)bq = Ebq - gb \cdot |q|$. Therefore another force $F_{gb|q}$ acts against the E-field.

$$F_{gb|q} = -g \cdot b \cdot |q| = -g \cdot b \cdot |e| = -9.81 \frac{m}{s^2} \cdot 11 \cdot 10^9 \frac{kg}{C} \cdot 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C = -1.72 \cdot 10^{-8} N$$

$$a = -\frac{1.72 \cdot 10^{-8}}{9.1 \cdot 10^{-31}} \cdot \frac{m}{s^2} = -1.8 \cdot 10^{22} \frac{m}{s^2} \leftrightarrow +2.6 \cdot 10^{13} \frac{m}{s^2} \text{ q.e.d.}$$

With other words: the g-field also couples with q and subsequently acts on the electrical charge. As a result the free electron is not only accelerated towards the sky but also towards the earth. Obviously both accelerations compensate each other widely. So it can be seen that this formalism can provide an explanation for the well known fact, that free electrons can exist on the surface of the earth and that they are not influenced too much by the E-field of the earth.

References

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